

Editorial

Relaunching *Individual Differences Research*: Bridging Past and Present

We are excited to announce the 2025 relaunch of *Individual Differences Research (IDR)*, providing a renewed platform for high-quality studies on individual differences. After a period of inactivity, the journal enters a new phase designed to honor its historical record while advancing contemporary scholarship.

As part of our relaunch strategy, we are undertaking two complementary initiatives:

- *Back Volumes Project*: Selected missing volumes from 2015–2024 will be reconstructed, featuring a mix of curated republished articles, previously unpublished works, and retrospective reviews. Many of these contributions come from our recently acquired archives from Psychological Publishing, including *Psychology Journal*, *Counseling and Clinical Psychology Journal*, and *Journal of Worry and Affective Experience*, chosen for their continuing relevance to our understanding of individual differences. We call these our “Archival Featured Articles.” DOI’s and proper dating will be added to each back volume to ensure reliable citation and indexing. Further, all previous volumes of *IDR* (Volumes 1–22) will gradually be made openly accessible on the journal’s website, expanding their availability to the scholarly community.
- *Current and New Research*: Volume 23 (2025) will publish new research on a rolling basis, with each article assigned a DOI and unique identifier. Articles will be released online shortly after acceptance. These articles will be grouped within an annual volume to ensure consistent organization and citation. From 2025 onward, authors will retain copyright of their published works while granting the journal broad publication rights, supporting both academic freedom and wide dissemination.

These changes reflect not only the journal’s renewed mission but also broader shifts in academic publishing over the past decade. Scholarship has become increasingly digital, with open-access models expanding the reach of research beyond traditional subscription barriers. Article-level identifiers such as DOIs and locators now play a central role in ensuring accessibility, discoverability, and citation accuracy. By embracing these developments, *IDR* aligns itself with contemporary publishing practices while maintaining continuity with its historical foundation.

In connection with this relaunch, the journal also adopts an updated publication format. Volumes 1–12 (2003–2014) were published with issue numbers and page ranges, consistent with print-era conventions. Beginning with the reconstructed back issues for 2015 onward, the journal transitions to an online-only system using article locators rather than issue numbers or page ranges. For citation purposes, earlier articles should continue to be referenced in their original format, while all articles from 2015 forward should be cited using the volume and article locator. This dual system preserves the integrity of the historical record while providing a sustainable and consistent approach for future issues.

Our approach is intended to preserve the continuity of *IDR*'s scholarly record while providing a platform for innovative contributions to the study of individual differences. By making archival and new content openly accessible, we aim to create a rich, cohesive resource that reflects both the historical depth and current developments in the field.

IDR remains committed to advancing understanding of individual differences (broadly defined). Our conception of individual differences includes any variable on which individuals or groups might be different. As throughout our history, these domains include behavioral, temperament, personality, affect, psychological processes, development, mental health, psychopathology, interests & values, social, cognitive, sleep and dreams, motivation, learning & change, stress & health, perception, and psychophysiology, among others.

We invite authors, reviewers, and readers to join us in this new chapter of *IDR*, bridging past scholarship with contemporary research that illuminates human experience.

William Kelly, Ph.D.
Founder and Editor, *Individual Differences Research*

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